

Message from GALA Choruses Executive Director

John D. Carrion

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Dear Reader,

I am so thrilled to invite you to read the inaugural edition of the Journal of Queer Choral Studies. This edition comes as the culmination of several years of scholarship and an entire year of administrative work to bring this journal from idea to fruition. The academic process is often a lonely journey but one that I truly believe is essential to the advancement of not only our theoretical understandings but also of our pragmatic approaches to the fundamental issues we face in our choirs, our societies, and even within ourselves.

I want to thank our Board of Directors for their support of this journal but, most of all, I want to thank Dr. Jessica Gallagher-Steuver for her tireless work to bring this journal to life. Her commitment to the rigor of the process and to the scholarship contained herein is one that will allow us to continue these conversations long into the future. I know that you will appreciate her dedication to this project as you learn from the work that her team has thoroughly vetted for inclusion.

Kind regards,

John D. Carrion
Executive Director
GALA Choruses

